

An Innovative Multi-scale Strategy-based Decision Engine for Zero-touch Management and Orchestration in 6G

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Abstract—In the upcoming era of 6G, mobile networks will need to handle demanding applications such as extended reality, digital twins, holographic telepresence, and immersive communication. They will also have to meet stricter application requirements across the edge cloud continuum. These new applications will raise expectations for performance, reliability, ubiquity, trustworthiness, security, openness, and sustainability that will drive innovation and bring about transformative changes across the architecture of future mobile networks. Zero-touch management will become a necessity for delivering the next generation of services in 6G networks with speed and agility, enabling network self-configuration, self-optimization, self-monitoring, and self-healing without further human intervention at both local and global scopes. Decision Engines (DEs), leveraging AI, will play a critical role in the orchestration and management of 6G networks by optimizing network performance and user experience through real-time, automated, and intelligent decisions. An innovative DE is proposed and empowered by Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning (HRL), a multi-scale strategy that orchestrates decisions across all network domains through local agents. The architectural and algorithmic assumptions of this DE will ensure efficient, scalable, and autonomous network operations, enhancing not only the performance and reliability of 6G networks but also paving the way for new applications and services that can leverage the full potential of next-generation connectivity.

Index Terms—Zero-touch Management, Decision Engine, Close Loop Automation, Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning, 6G Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

In the transition from the 5G era to the Beyond-5G/5G-Advanced, and eventually, to the 6G era, mobile communications infrastructure will need to be redesigned to accommodate the demanding requirements of futuristic applications beyond the capabilities of current 5G networks. As we approach the next decade and the widespread deployment of 6G, the types of applications supported by 5G will evolve, improving existing service classes such as Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC), Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), and Massive Machine-Type Communication (mMTC) while introducing new services. In the upcoming 6G era, the combination of the Internet of Things (IoT),

humans, connected devices, vehicles, robots, and drones will generate an immense amount of digital data. Therefore, 6G technology will need to handle more complex applications such as holographic telepresence and immersive communication, meeting increasingly stringent requirements along the edge-cloud continuum [1], [2].

Internet of Senses, IoT, and Digital Twins will be the main factors for content generation and network traffic in 6G, setting new expectations for performance, reliability, accessibility, trustworthiness, security, openness, and sustainability. Also, they will require networks to match the agility of the cloud, as new use cases focus on service-based models and performance-sensitive applications at the edge. This means using new mobile networks that can support applications requiring over 100 Gbps throughput, very low latency, support for a large number of devices, higher availability and reliability, extreme positioning accuracy, inclusiveness, and social acceptance while considering the UN's Sustainable Development Goals [3].

One promising solution to address the requirements mentioned above is efficiently deploying Network Function Virtualization (NFV) in the network. However, deploying VNFs in 6G networks introduces new challenges, such as ensuring optimal performance and low latency across highly distributed and dynamic environments while meeting the Quality of Service (QoS) restrictions. In addition, resource allocation for dynamic scaling and placement of the VNFs needs to be met according to the varying demands of different network slices and services due to the diverse range of technological domains (edge, far-edge, cloud). This can ensure reliability and minimize the downtime during VNF updates or migrations during the complicated deployment. For this reason, there is a need to introduce an automated platform to manage and orchestrate the VNFs' placement in the network efficiently.

To address the limitations of traditional VNFs, the concept of Cloud Network Functions (CNFs) has been introduced. CNFs are specifically designed for dynamic cloud environments and utilize a microservices architecture, distinguishing

them from traditional VNFs. Unlike VNFs, which typically rely on virtual machines, CNFs leverage advanced orchestration tools, enabling more resilient and scalable network management. This approach not only enhances the adaptability and efficiency of network functions but also ensures better resource utilization across distributed network environments, including edge, far-edge, and cloud domains. Additionally, CNFs support the seamless integration of new services and capabilities, enabling networks to adapt quickly to changes in dynamic environments. Thus, to support flexible and scalable CNF deployment across various network environments while automatically maintaining Service Level Agreements (SLA) to ensure network resilience, a DE can be integrated into the 6G networks.

To this end, this paper focuses on the description of the DE as a principal component of the closed-loop functions that Management and Orchestration comprise, as it is important to ensure continuous optimization of infrastructure, services, and applications based on monitored data. The closed-loop functions create a sophisticated and dynamic 6G network ecosystem capable of achieving the ambitious goals set for 6G and realizing a future-ready 6G network landscape. The general block architecture of the closed-loop functions includes the Analytics Engine (AE), the Monitoring System (MS), and the actors that are interconnected with the DE. The main contributions of this paper lie in the description of the DE architectural design and functional blocks with an emphasis on the role and functionalities of 'Decision Making' (DM), where an innovative AI-based methodology is adopted for its foundation.

The DE can derive substantial advantages from AI-driven techniques in multiple ways, including the augmentation of its capabilities, efficiency, and optimizing its operations. Utilizing AI methodologies, such as ML algorithms, enables the DE to elevate and customize analytics on extensive and complex datasets. This improvement allows for more precise, subtle, and individualized decision-making by uncovering patterns and correlations, which proves especially beneficial in challenging domains like resource allocation, scheduling, and logistics, where specifying the optimal solution amid numerous possibilities is complex. Moreover, the DE can proactively leverage predictive ML algorithms to make decisions and plan for dynamic scenarios such as real-time data processing, facilitating and enabling swift and well-informed decision-making. Finally, integrating Natural Language Processing (NLP) assists the DE in making comprehensive decisions by extracting insights from diverse sources such as unstructured datasets [4], [5].

Due to this fact, to address the aforementioned challenges in 6G networks, this paper proposes the integration of Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning (HRL) into the DE environment [6]–[8].

The remainder of this article is structured as follows. In Section II, we highlight the relevant studies in the literature. The overview of the DE is elaborated in Section III. Section IV, explains the selected methodology for designing intelligent decision-making, which is followed by a list of the

most relevant evaluation metrics in V. Finally, in Section VI, we provide final remarks and future work.

II. RELATED WORK

The DE, as part of the closed-loop functions, consists of RL agents that manage 6G networks and optimize problems. The DE monitors these agents, makes arbitration decisions, and dynamically adjusts DRL objective functions to accommodate varying operating conditions and performance goals. To solve complex optimization problems, AI/ML methodologies like the HRL method can be implemented. HRL algorithms have been introduced for real-time adaptation to fluctuating and dynamic optimization problems, but their implementation has not received much attention, especially for facilitating ultra-high capacity, low latency, and service-aware and orchestration management in different technological domains for networking optimization problems. Therefore, there is still room for integrating HRL within DE to automatically manage 6G networks.

According to the existing literature, the HRL technique is primarily implemented in the robotics field to address the decomposition of complex problems, breaking down a complex task into simpler, reusable tasks [4]. Additionally, HRL is applied in behavioural and navigation control scenarios, such as the one presented in [9]. In this paper, the authors introduce a hybrid HRL-based algorithm capable of generalizing training samples with a function approximator, which automatically decomposes the state space, thus eliminating the need for task-specific designs. Furthermore, a recent work utilizes an HRL-based algorithm that defines agents to tackle multi-stage task problems by applying a Soft Actor-Critic (SAC) approach, which adjusts the policy of each agent to maximize both the current and next agent critic [10].

While HRL is less common in networking compared to robotics, it isn't fully absent. In the networking domain, it can be applied in scenarios where hierarchical decision-making and task decomposition can be beneficial. For instance, in [11], the O-RAN orchestration for near real-time applications is achieved through an HRL-based mechanism that optimizes Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and manages the applications to offer the best and most optimal orchestration of near real-time applications given the intent operator. Resource allocation problems can benefit from HRL as well by decomposing the complex task into several sub-tasks [12], where the authors tackled this challenge in an IoT scenario by employing Hierarchical Deep Reinforcement Learning (HDRL). A more advanced iteration of the HRL concept is outlined in [13], where a Meta-HRL is suggested for vehicular networks. In one of the most recent research works [14], a multi-agent HRL is introduced for an industrial automation scenario to fulfil URLLC requirements in 6G networks.

Despite the consideration of certain aspects of 6G requirements in the aforementioned works, they fall short of incorporating energy efficiency into the network, a crucial element within the control loops of 6G communications. To the best of our knowledge, in the available state-of-the-art, Hierarchical Intentional-Unintentional-SAC (HIU-SAC)

has never been implemented in the networking area or its relevant optimization problems (e.g., energy efficiency of SFC placement, service delay minimization). Therefore, to address the current gaps in the existing literature and overcome the management and orchestration-based challenges while meeting crucial elements of 6G communication, this paper integrates an HRL framework within the DE.

III. DECISION ENGINE OVERVIEW

This section first outlines the high-level architecture of the DE, emphasizing its critical role and integration with other components within the closed-loop functions block. Then, the detail of essential elements of the DE and their respective responsibilities in executing control algorithms and facilitating decision-making actions will be explained.

A. High-level Architecture of DE

According to the ETSI GS ZSM [15], the closed-loop functions block comprises four primary elements: monitoring, analysis, decision, and execution. During the monitoring phase, raw data from various sources is systematically gathered and pre-processed. Then, the collected data is transmitted to the analysis stage, where insights are derived to inform decision-making. In the execution stage, these decisions are translated into actionable commands, producing the desired outcomes.

To encapsulate this process, the link between the analysis element and the decision stage ensures that data from the monitoring phase, whether real-time or non-real-time, undergoes thorough analysis. This process refines analytic models and initiates or concludes analytical processes, supporting effective decision-making. Additionally, the connection between the decision phase and the execution phase involves defining a set of action plans. These plans refine decision models and facilitate the initiation and termination of decision processes. It is crucial to highlight that the decision stage can interact with other closed loops or external entities. This interaction allows for initiating or terminating decision processes, fine-tuning decision model configurations, retrieving outcomes from decision functions, and making decisions for external entities or other closed loops.

Fig. 1. High-level Architecture of DE.

As depicted in Fig. 1, the DE is interconnected with the AE, MS, and ACT, in which the ACT can potentially be

located in various technical domains such as Far Edge, Edge, or Cloud. The MS, which is responsible for collecting raw data or information, can transmit this data to the DE or AE. Alternatively, there is an option to store the data in an online memory store (illustrated as the yellow cylinder in Fig. 1). Leveraging an online memory store enhances the processing flexibility and length of both AE and DE without compromising the data sampling conducted by the MS. The AE can receive stored information and process it for DE utilization. The processed data may include predictions, classifications, and other relevant insights. Alternatively, the AE can receive raw measurements directly from the MS, although this process necessitates synchronization. It is imperative to note that the External User Interface (EUI) plays a crucial role in defining and modifying the configurations of the DE (e.g., discount factor in DRL algorithms), AE (e.g., prediction interval), MS (e.g., granularity), and actuation.

Furthermore, the DE can acquire processed information, such as predicted KPIs, either by reading from the online memory store or directly receiving it from the AE. Additionally, the DE can access raw data or information directly from the MS. Once decisions are made, the DE can store them, along with AI metrics, in the online memory store or transmit them directly to the actuators for implementation. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the DE can effectively send these decisions to the ACT [16].

B. DE Architectural Design

As depicted in Fig. 2, the DE is a sophisticated system that consists of three primary blocks: input pre-processor, control trigger, and output pre-processor (highlighted in cyan functional blocks).

The input pre-processing block is primarily responsible for extracting insights and learning from raw data across diverse domains, determining which knowledge is pertinent for subsequent processing within the DE. Considering the distinct languages of various data sources and protocols, the data ingestion process employs diverse implementations customized to meet specific operational needs. Afterwards, the data normalization procedure is pivotal in ensuring data format and structure uniformity. The input pre-processing block directly links the control trigger process and comprises three key sub-blocks: situation awareness, Model-Driven Engineering (MDE), and policy management. The situation awareness functional block perceives and comprehends elements within the current scenario, projecting data into future states. In the MDE functional block, decisions are made regarding implementing selected actions derived from the situation awareness functional block based on software development principles. In addition, the policy management sub-block orchestrates the transformation of data and information from their native formats into structures conducive to generating outputs intelligible to assistive systems.

Finally, the processed data proceeds to the output pre-processing process, which undergoes translation into a format understandable for external users or actuators (denormalization functional block). According to Fig. 2, a broker or

message bus acts as a gateway, facilitating communication between different technical domains and effectively decoupling DE from other technical domains (long blue block).

Fig. 2. Functional blocks of DE.

IV. DECISION-MAKING

In this section, the analysis focuses on the block of intelligent DM. Its functionality is based on control algorithms, especially RL methods. The HIU-SAC algorithm has been adopted as it combines the strengths of hierarchical reinforcement learning and maximum entropy RL to solve the CNF placement problem effectively. By integrating SAC for high-level strategic decisions and Dueling Double Deep Q-Networks (D3QN) [17] for precise low-level actions, and incorporating inverse utility for stability, HIU-SAC achieves robust, efficient, and optimal CNF placement in complex network environments. In short, in the high level of hierarchy, the HIU-SAC tackles strategic decision-making, which considers high-level objectives such as network-wide performance and fairness in resource allocation across different edge nodes. This can provide a coarse-grained placement strategy for CNFs. However, in the low level of the hierarchy, by deploying the D3QN algorithm, it is possible to handle the less complex decision-making, which focuses on fine-tuning the placement within the options provided by HIU-SAC by considering metrics such as resource availability, communication cost, and specific service requirements of each CNF. Therefore, the next subsection is dedicated to the concept of HRL that guides DE in decision-making.

A. HRL Fundamentals

In this section, the concept of HRL is elaborated, detailing how the DE gains advantages from its application. HRL offers a method for tackling complex tasks by breaking them into more manageable sub-tasks through a hierarchical structure of policies established via RL. In this hierarchical arrangement, the high-level policy typically selects sub-tasks as its actions for the global task. This high-level policy is trained to execute the global task by considering the sequence of its sub-tasks, guided by the rewards acquired during the global task. At a lower tier of the hierarchy, a sub-task

identified by the higher level becomes an independent RL problem. Here, a lower-level policy is developed to carry out that specific sub-task, guided by the internal rewards associated with it. It is essential to mention that the global task reward may also be incorporated optionally. The lowest-level policies are responsible for selecting fundamental actions, referred to as primitive actions. Fig. 3, presents a simplified schematic of the HRL, featuring two layers of hierarchy. The communication between these layers, the environment, and the agent is illustrated with arrows [18].

Fig. 3. Fundamental schematic of the HRL.

Here, π represents the policy (π_l policy and π_h policy at the low level and high levels, respectively). Moreover, s, a and r show the state, action and reward, respectively. In addition, o is the option policy selection or high-level action [18]. Therefore, HRL offers a comprehensive approach to DE where it can address complex optimization problems by systematically decomposing complicated tasks into more manageable sub-tasks. This results in a more efficient learning process, ensuring rapid convergence without a significant increase in sensitivity to hyperparameters and enhancing the overall robustness of the learning process. The adaptability of HRL is beneficial in continuous domains and real-time applications -considered one of the 6G network aspects- allowing the agent and decision-making process to adjust effectively. Moreover, HRL excels in controlling temporal abstract actions, providing a flexible framework capable of handling tasks with extended time scales and complex temporal dependencies more effectively.

1) **HIU-SAC Concept Description:** Details of the HRL-based optimization algorithm, derived from the SAC algorithm in [19] to meet the objectives of the DE, are explained here. To bridge the existing gap in the literature and tackle the challenges mentioned before, we adopt a novel HRL framework from the robotic field to the considered 6G network architecture. Our proposed approach excels in coordinating the parameters of Energy Efficiency (EE) in communications while catering to the demanding needs of extreme Enhanced eMBB, extreme URLLC, and extreme mMTC services. This adaptable framework is capable of expanding beyond two hierarchical layers, with each high-level agent tasked with orchestrating a specific technological

domain and addressing particular requirements/tasks. For example, an efficient and elastic placement of the VNFs to reduce energy consumption in the telecom network can be achieved through this framework. In addition, this could reduce the operational expenses of the service providers while maintaining the SLA.

The adopted HRL framework, initially developed for complex robotic tasks, has been adjusted for the networking domain in this work. Modifying and adapting the algorithm to suit the telecommunication requirements can address intricate, real-time management and orchestration challenges for multiple technological domains at different levels of network operations. The HRL framework incorporates a multi-task SAC algorithm referred to as the HIU-SAC algorithm, in which the intentional behaviours provide high-level guidance and strategic planning whereas, unintentional behaviours handle low-level and real-time environmental interaction. This algorithm is designed to scale across all the tasks gathered. In addition, it enables, not only, the enhancement of its associated policy through a single sub-task but also indirectly benefits numerous other process policies. This level of improvement in this SAC algorithm will demonstrate how deep neural network policies and value functions can be learned, even when employing an arbitrarily chosen behaviour policy, and increase decision-making flexibility. In conclusion, integrating the HIU-SAC algorithm into the telecommunication environment, specifically 6G network architecture, serves a double purpose: strengthening network resilience (i.e., real-time adaptation and resource optimization such as bandwidth allocation, delay minimization and energy efficiency) and advancing QoS (i.e., proactive management).

2) **HIU-SAC Algorithm:** To decompose a complex problem optimization, the HIU-SAC algorithm defines two types of policies: compound and composable. Within the learning process of the HIU-SAC algorithm, the high-level policy π_h is called compound, and several low-level policies $\pi_l^{[n]}$ are called composable. This terminology is inherited from the related tasks with these policies discriminating them into compound and composable as well. The number of the latter, assuming N , depends on the number of sub-tasks that the high-level complex task is decomposed.

The composable tasks $T^{[n]}$ and the corresponding composable policies $\pi_l^{[n]}$ (modelled as Gaussian distributions) are formulated and treated as independent RL problems, enabling this algorithm to execute different policies concurrently. The decision-making process of each RL agent is modeled as an MDP which is defined by the tuple $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, p_s, r^{[n]})$. All sub-tasks $\{T^{[n]}\}_{n=1}^N$ share the same state and action space $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A})$ and differ in terms of the reward function $r^{[n]}$. Also, $r^{[n]}$ is a function that depends on the environment state $s_t \in \mathcal{S}$ and action $a_t \in \mathcal{A}$ at time step t and affects the transition probability $p_s = p(s_{(t+1)}|s_t, a_t)$. A key aspect of the HIU-SAC algorithm is that it is built on a maximum entropy RL approach to assist exploration during the learning process. The maximum entropy of the agent policy is used to quantify the randomness of the actions given the state and is included in the RL objective function.

Assuming a more complex compound task M , described as a composition of tasks in T , M will share the same state space, action space, and transition probability, but a different reward $r^M(s_t, a_t)$ in the resulting MDP $(\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, p_s, r^M)$. The related compound policy π^M is defined reusing the set of composable policies $\Pi = \{\pi_l^{[n]}\}_{n=1}^N$ defined in T and using a set of activation vectors $W = \{w^{[n]}\}_{(n=1)}^N$ whose components are used to combine each action vector. Thus, the compound policy is modelled as a 2-level hierarchical policy $\pi^M = g(W, \Pi)$.

A Neural Network (NN) is used to model the function for acquiring the state-dependent activation vectors and composable policies T and another NN with different parameters to model the Q-functions of both the composable policies T and compound policy M . To solve task M , it simultaneously learns the required set of composable policies and activation vectors for a compound policy π^M by adopting an off-policy multi-task policy search. Therefore, the compound policy π^M , which the agent follows to interact with the environment, is called intentional policy. In contrast, the composable policies, or, in other words, the target policies in the off-policy setting, are called unintentional. For this reason, the training process algorithm with the combination of SAC is called HIU-SAC which is summarized in [4].

3) **Fine-Grained Actions:** For refined low-level decision-making, the D3QNs algorithm is utilized. The approach of D3QNs addresses more granular and specific placement decisions within the options provided by the high-level HIU-SAC strategy. This algorithm focuses on fine-tuning CNF placement by considering metrics such as resource utilization and the specific service requirements of each CNF. By leveraging D3QNs, the system can make subtle and precise adjustments to CNF placements, ensuring optimal resource utilization and mitigating performance and service availability constraints. In the context of CNF placement, the D3QN algorithm enhances the decision-making process by providing more accurate and stable action-value estimates. The hierarchical approach, with HIU-SAC handling high-level strategic decisions and DDDQN handling low-level actions, ensures optimal placement of CNFs by continuously adapting to the dynamic network environment. This dual-level decision-making framework allows for both macro-level optimization, such as overall network performance and resource fairness, and micro-level adjustments, such as resource availability and communication costs, leading to efficient and effective CNF management.

Notably, the low-level decision-making is finalized by a learning process that is built upon a feedback mechanism that observes the outcomes of the executed actions and the consequent state of the environment, ensuring that learning is grounded in the most recent experiences.

V. EVALUATION METRICS

The DE plays a pivotal role in ensuring both QoS and Quality of Experience (QoE) in advanced 6G networks [20]. While traditional networking KPIs—such as ultra-low latency (0.1-1 ms), peak throughput, and EE - remain fundamental,

the AI-driven components of the DE, particularly the integration of HIU-SAC and D3QN algorithms, introduce additional performance metrics that are equally important. The AI-specific KPIs provide a comprehensive understanding of how well the DE manages complex and real-time decisions.

More specifically, in the evaluation of the HRL-based DE using the HIU-SAC and D3QN frameworks, KPIs help to determine the effectiveness of the DM in network management, service orchestration, and resource allocation. The combination of HIU-SAC for high-level DM and D3QN for granular actions ensures a robust approach to complex optimization problems in network management. Specifically, HIU-SAC handles the strategic, high-level DM's objectives, such as network-wide efficiency and resource distribution across nodes, allowing the DE to make rapid adjustments. Meanwhile, D3QN provides real-time, more refined, low-level optimization, making decisions concerning specific resource allocations and communication costs. Together, these methodologies can achieve improved convergence speed and adaptability to dynamic network conditions like 6G, where ultra-low latency is a priority. Convergence speed is critical in determining how quickly the learning algorithms reach optimal decisions, and, indeed, the HIU-SAC and D3QN algorithms that work in tandem can ensure this efficiency.

Besides convergence time, sample complexity, which measures the learning efficiency of the algorithms from data, is optimized by HIU-SAC's broad-scale adjustments, reducing the need for extensive data samples whilst D3QN ensures refined, resource-efficient learning. As the problem size increases, with more states and actions, the DE, with the synergy of these algorithms, remains scalable, balancing both high-level and granular decision-making without compromising performance. Fast convergence and insensitivity to problem scale are essential to handle the vast state and action spaces of 6G networks. Robustness in dynamic environments and responsiveness to real-time changes further showcase the ability of HIU-SAC and D3QN to quickly comprehend their surroundings and subsequently leverage their rewards to maintain optimal performance. In conclusion, this framework enables the DE to meet requirements, such as ultra-low latency, high throughput, and EE, which are crucial for service delivery and sustainability in 6G networks.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The design of the DE architecture in the 6G network architecture and its integration with an HRL-based algorithm are the main topics of this study. Additionally, it offers details on the DE's capabilities and how zero-touch administration may enhance the coordination between technical domains. In future work, the modified HRL-based algorithm will be expanded into more than two levels of hierarchy by adding an intermediate level to extend the automation of the DE's capabilities (e.g., dynamic placement of SFC for 6G services). This approach will improve continuous resource allocation, context-aware adjustments, and predictive service management while maintaining the SLA and prioritizing sustainability.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Banafaa, I. Shayea, J. Din, M. H. Azmi, A. Alashbi, Y. I. Daradkeh, and A. Alhammedi, "6g mobile communication technology: Requirements, targets, applications, challenges, advantages, and opportunities," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 64, pp. 245–274, 2023.
- [2] M. Giordani, M. Polese, M. Mezzavilla, S. Rangan, and M. Zorzi, "Toward 6g networks: Use cases and technologies," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 55–61, 2020.
- [3] J. R. Bhat and S. A. Alqahtani, "6g ecosystem: Current status and future perspective," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 43134–43167, 2021.
- [4] D. Esteban, L. Rozo, and D. G. Caldwell, "Hierarchical reinforcement learning for concurrent discovery of compound and composable policies," in *Proc. IROS, 2019*, pp. 1818–1825, IEEE, 2019.
- [5] Z. Yang, K. Merrick, L. Jin, and H. A. Abbass, "Hierarchical deep reinforcement learning for continuous action control," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, vol. 29, no. 11, pp. 5174–5184, 2018.
- [6] H. A. Akyıldız, Ö. F. Gemici, I. Hökelek, and H. A. Çirpan, "Multi-objective resource allocation for 5G using hierarchical reinforcement learning," in *Proc. BlackSeaCom, 2022*, pp. 202–207, IEEE, 2022.
- [7] W. SHI, *Improving the Performance of URLLC Using Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning*. PhD thesis, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2023.
- [8] Y. Dai, D. Xu, K. Zhang, Y. Lu, S. Maharjan, and Y. Zhang, "Deep reinforcement learning for edge computing and resource allocation in 5G beyond," in *Proc. ICCT, 2019*, pp. 866–870, IEEE, 2019.
- [9] Y. Zhou and H. W. Ho, "Online robot guidance and navigation in non-stationary environment with hybrid hierarchical reinforcement learning," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 114, p. 105152, 2022.
- [10] J. Erskine and C. Lehnert, "Developing cooperative policies for multi-stage reinforcement learning tasks," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 6590–6597, 2022.
- [11] M. A. Habib, H. Zhou, P. E. Iturria-Rivera, M. Elsayed, M. Bavand, R. Gaigalas, Y. Ozcan, and M. Erol-Kantarci, "Intent-driven intelligent control and orchestration in o-ran via hierarchical reinforcement learning," in *Proc. MASS, 2023*, pp. 55–61, IEEE, 2023.
- [12] H. A. Shah, L. Zhao, and I.-M. Kim, "Joint network control and resource allocation for space-terrestrial integrated network through hierarchical deep actor-critic reinforcement learning," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 70, no. 5, pp. 4943–4954, 2021.
- [13] Y. He, Y. Wang, Q. Lin, and J. Li, "Meta-hierarchical reinforcement learning (mhlrl)-based dynamic resource allocation for dynamic vehicular networks," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 3495–3506, 2022.
- [14] W. Shi, M. Ganjalzadeh, H. S. Ghadikolaei, and M. Petrova, "Communication-efficient orchestrations for urllc service via hierarchical reinforcement learning," in *Proc. PIMRC*, pp. 1–6, IEEE, 2023.
- [15] G. ETSI, "Zero-touch network and service management (zsm); closed loop automation; part 1: enablers [J]," *Group Specification (GS) ETSI GS ZSM*, 2021.
- [16] L.B. ORA-FR, F. Guillemin, R. Tępiński, M. Rosiński, J. Jegier, S. Thrasyvoulos, P. Doanis and A. Ksentini, "Deliverable d4. 2 final report on ai-driven techniques for the monb5g decision engine," 2019.
- [17] M. Gök, "Dynamic path planning via dueling double deep q-network (d3qn) with prioritized experience replay," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 158, p. 111503, 2024.
- [18] S. Pateria, B. Subagdja, A.-h. Tan, and C. Quek, "Hierarchical reinforcement learning: A comprehensive survey," *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, vol. 54, no. 5, pp. 1–35, 2021.
- [19] T. Haarnoja, A. Zhou, P. Abbeel, and S. Levine, "Soft actor-critic: Off-policy maximum entropy deep reinforcement learning with a stochastic actor," in *Proc. International conference on machine learning, 2018*, pp. 1861–1870, PMLR, 2018.
- [20] S. Zhang and D. Zhu, "Towards artificial intelligence enabled 6g: State of the art, challenges, and opportunities," *Computer Networks*, vol. 183, p. 107556, 2020.